

Syntheses of 1,5-benzothiazepines. Part XL : Syntheses and antimicrobial studies of 10-substituted-6a,7-dihydro-6-(4-methoxyphenyl/phenyl)-7-(3-nitrophenyl)-6H-[1]benzopyrano[3,4-c][1,5]benzothiazepines

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Abstract : The reactions of exocyclic α,β -unsaturated ketones, the benzylidene flavanones, 3-(3-nitrobenzylidene)-4'-methoxyflavanone and 3-(3-nitrobenzylidene)flavanone, with 5-substituted-2-aminobenzenethiols, the substituents being halogeno, alkyl and alkoxy, have been carried out in dry ethanol with catalytic amounts of trifluoroacetic acid. The twelve new compounds, 10-substituted-6a,7-dihydro-6-(4-methoxyphenyl/phenyl)-7-(3-nitrophenyl)-6H-[1]benzopyrano[3,4-c][1,5]benzothiazepines, were synthesized and characterized by microestimations for C, H, N and S and IR, NMR and mass spectral studies. The synthesized compounds were screened for antimicrobial activity against the Gram-positive bacteria, *Staphylococcus aureus* and Gram-negative bacteria, *Enterobacter cloacae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and the fungus, *Candida albicans*, with reference drugs, Vancomycin, Cefoperazone/Sulbactam, Meropenem and Fluconazole, respectively. Most of the compounds showed promising bioactivity.

Keywords : Exocyclic, benzylidene flavanone, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Enterobacter cloacae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Candida albicans*.

Introduction

Most of the patented 1,4- and 1,5-benzodiazepines, e.g. Clobazam¹, Clonazepam², Triflubarazam³, Flurazepam⁴, Midazolam⁵, Chlorazepate⁶, Diazepam⁷, Flumazenil⁸ are well known for their psychotropic activities but the structurally related tetracyclic benzopyranobenzodiazepine drug, 'Zimet' has been reported⁹ to possess antineoplastic activity against dreadful diseases like leukemia, melanoma-B₁₆, Lewis lung carcinoma etc. But, tetracyclic benzopyranobenzothiazepines have been reported to show cardiovascular properties, like anti-arrhythmic¹⁰, anti-ischemic¹¹, coronary vasodilator¹², analogous to the 1,5-benzothiazepine cardiovascular drugs, diltiazem¹³, siratiazem¹⁴, clentiazem¹⁵ etc.

Expecting that the fusion of benzopyran ring with the thiazepine nucleus, besides having a substituent in the fused benzene ring of the benzothiazepine ring system, may impart bioactivity to the compound, syntheses of different series of benzopyranobenzothiazepines have been undertaken and reported earlier¹⁶⁻²².

The reactions of variously substituted arylidene fla-

vanones have been reported²³⁻²⁶ to be performed with six 5-substituted-2-aminobenzenethiols, the substituents being halogeno - fluoro, chloro, bromo; alkyl as methyl and alkoxy as methoxy and ethoxy, in various reaction conditions like neutral, acidic and basic medium.

In continuation of our constant efforts in exploring the syntheses and probable bioactivity of substituted benzopyranobenzothiazepines, we herein report the syntheses of twelve new compounds, 10-substituted-6a,7-dihydro-6-(4-methoxyphenyl/phenyl)-7-(3-nitrophenyl)-6H-[1]benzopyrano[3,4-c][1,5]benzothiazepines in dry ethanol containing catalytic amount of trifluoroacetic acid and the final products were obtained in a single step.

All the newly synthesized compounds were then screened for their relative antimicrobial activity, comprising antibacterial and antifungal activity. These were carried out against the Gram-positive bacteria, *Staphylococcus aureus* and the Gram-negative bacteria, *Enterobacter cloacae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and antifungal activity was carried out against the fungus, *Candida albicans*, by using the paper disc method with res-

pect to reference drugs Vancomycin, Cefoperazone/Sulbactam, Meropenem and Fluconazole, respectively.

Results and discussion

Equimolar quantities of the 5-substituted-2-amino benzenethiols (**1a-f**) were reacted with the benzylidene flavanones, 3-(3-nitrobenzylidene)-4'-methoxy flavanone (**2a**) and 3-(3-nitrobenzylidene)flavanone (**2b**) respectively, in dry ethanol containing trifluoroacetic acid as catalyst, by refluxing them for 6–8 h.

The crude, so obtained, on crystallization from ethanol, afforded the final products, 10-substituted-6a,7-dihydro-6-(4-methoxyphenyl)-7-(3-nitrophenyl)-6H-[1]benzopyrano[3,4-c][1,5]benzothiazepines (**3a-f**) and 10-substituted-6a,7-dihydro-6-phenyl-7-(3-nitrophenyl)-6H-[1]benzopyrano[3,4-c][1,5]benzothiazepines (**3g-l**) in 52–65% yields (Table 1). The reactions are understood to take place by the protonation of the carbonyl group of the arylidene flavanones (**2a, b**), which makes the methine

carbon electron deficient and thus susceptible to nucleophilic attack by the sulphhydryl electrons of the 5-substituted-2-aminobenzenethiols (**1a-f**). The intermediates, so generated, undergo dehydrative cyclisation to give the final products **3a-l** (Scheme 1), in a single step.

The IR spectrum of the arylidene flavanone (**2a**) showed aromatic $\nu(\text{C-H})$ vibrations at around 3010 cm^{-1} and skeletal vibrations appeared at 1500, 1469, 1360, 1300 and aliphatic $\nu(\text{C-H})$ absorption found at 2920 cm^{-1} respectively, the absorption band at 1675 cm^{-1} and 1612 cm^{-1} indicated the presence of carbonyl and C=C group.

Compounds **3a-f**, **3k** and **3l** showed strong and medium intensity absorptions in the range, $1312\text{--}1318\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to $\nu(\text{C-O-C})$ of the alkoxy group. Absorptions in the range $1612\text{--}1602\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which is characteristic $\nu(\text{C=N})$, indicate that the amino group of the thiol and the carbonyl group of the arylidene flavanones have reacted to form carbon nitrogen double bond in **3a-l**. Hence, it may be concluded that under the present reaction con-

Table 1. Physical constants and micro analytical data of **3a-c** and **3e-l**

Compd.	X	M.p. (°C)	R_f	Yield (%)	Molecular formula (Mol. wt.)	Elemental analysis (%):			
						Found (Calcd.)			
						C	H	N	S
3a	F	136–137	0.91	65.19	$\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{21}\text{FN}_2\text{O}_4\text{S}$ (512)	–	–	5.41 (5.47)	5.80 (6.26)
3b	Cl	112–113	0.85	61.69	$\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{21}\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_4\text{S}$ (529)	65.90 (65.84)	4.02 (4.00)	–	–
3c	Br	90–92	0.83	61.14	$\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{21}\text{BrN}_2\text{O}_4\text{S}$ (573)	–	–	4.85 (4.89)	4.90 (5.59)
3e	OCH_3	78–80	0.89	64.16	$\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_2\text{O}_5\text{S}$ (524)	68.59 (68.59)	4.58 (4.61)	–	–
3f	OC_2H_5	84–85	0.88	59.20	$\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_2\text{O}_5\text{S}$ (538)	–	–	5.23 (5.20)	5.20 (5.95)
3g	F	142–143	0.71	67.45	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{19}\text{FN}_2\text{O}_3\text{S}$ (482)	69.58 (69.70)	3.98 (3.97)	–	–
3h	Cl	150–151	0.67	52.15	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{19}\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_3\text{S}$ (499)	74.10 (67.40)	4.18 (3.84)	–	–
3i	Br	135–136	0.68	55.20	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{19}\text{BrN}_2\text{O}_3\text{S}$ (543)	–	–	5.20 (5.15)	5.10 (5.90)
3j	CH_3	131–133	0.82	63.61	$\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{S}$ (478)	73.12 (73.15)	4.85 (4.91)	–	–
3k	OCH_3	140–141	0.72	58.28	$\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{S}$ (494)	–	–	3.65 (5.66)	8.41 (6.48)
3l	OC_2H_5	155–156	0.70	62.18	$\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{S}$ (508)	70.89 (70.85)	4.70 (4.76)	–	–

Compd.	X	R	Compd.	X	R
3a	F	OCH ₃	3g	F	H
3b	Cl	OCH ₃	3h	Cl	H
3c	Br	OCH ₃	3i	Br	H
3d	CH ₃	OCH ₃	3j	CH ₃	H
3e	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	3k	OCH ₃	H
3f	OC ₂ H ₅	OCH ₃	3l	OC ₂ H ₅	H

Scheme 1

ditions, the intermediates get cyclized by concerted mechanism to give the final products.

In the ¹H NMR spectrum of the 3-(3-nitrobenzylidene)-4'-methoxy flavanone (2a), two broad singlets were observed at δ 7.46 and 7.91 due to the long range allylic coupling of C₂-H and =C-H. The aromatic C-5 proton

absorbs downfield at δ 7.93, due to the deshielding effect of the carbonyl group, characteristic of the flavanone system. Compounds 3a-l showed two doublets, integrating for one proton each, in the downfield region at around δ 4.83-4.94 (1H, d, *J* 12.2 Hz) and 5.01-5.06 (1H, d, *J* 1.2 Hz). The two doublets in downfield region at around

Table 2. Characteristic ^1H NMR data (CDCl_3 , δ values in ppm, J in Hz) of **3a-c** and **3e-l**

Compd.	OCH_3 (3H, s)	$\text{C}_{6a}\text{-H}$ (dd, $J_1 = 12.2$, $J_2 = 1.2$)	$\text{C}_7\text{-H}$ (d, $J = 12.2$)	$\text{C}_6\text{-H}$ (d, $J = 1.2$)	$\text{C}_{10}\text{-XH}$	Aromatic proton (15H, m)
3a	3.88	3.36	4.85	5.01	–	6.90–8.09
3b	3.87	3.34	4.94	5.03	–	6.85–8.05
3c	3.88	3.40	4.83	5.02	–	6.81–7.96
3e	3.86	3.37	4.90	5.06	3.87 (3H, s)	6.91–7.93
3f	3.86	3.65	4.93	5.04	1.45 (3H, t, J 6) 4.10 (2H, q, J 6)	6.91–7.96
3g	–	3.63	4.92	5.04	–	6.74–8.10
3h	–	3.61	4.91	5.02	–	6.82–8.12
3i	–	3.56	4.90	5.03	–	6.81–8.21
3j	–	3.65	4.94	5.04	2.39 (3H, s)	7.22–8.27
3k	–	3.65	4.94	5.04	3.85 (3H, s)	7.02–7.98
3l	–	3.65	4.93	5.04	1.46 (3H, t, J 6) 4.10 (2H, q, J 6)	7.02–7.97

δ 4.83–4.94 and 5.01–5.06 may be assigned to $\text{C}_7\text{-H}$ and $\text{C}_6\text{-H}$, because these protons are attached to sp^3 carbons which are adjacent to electronegative oxygen and sulfur atom, respectively. A doublet of a doublet was observed at around δ 3.34–3.65 (1H, dd, J_1 12.2 Hz, J_2 1.2 Hz). This doublet of a doublet may be assigned to $\text{C}_{6a}\text{-H}$, due to the coupling of $\text{C}_{6a}\text{-H}$ with $\text{C}_6\text{-H}$ and $\text{C}_7\text{-H}$ (Table 2).

The mass spectra of the compounds **3b** and **3c** showed cluster of molecular ion peaks, **3b** showing molecular ion peaks at m/z 529, 531 and 533, corresponding to M^+ , $[\text{M}+2]^+$ and $[\text{M}+4]^+$ respectively while **3c** showed M^+ peak at 573, $[\text{M}+2]^+$ peak at 575 and $[\text{M}+4]^+$ peak at 577. The clusterous pattern of the molecular ion peaks and their intensities in compounds **3b** and **3c** affirmed the presence of halogens, chlorine and bromine. Similar clusterous pattern of M^+ and $[\text{M}+2]^+$ peaks at m/z 499 and 501 in **3h** and at 543 and 545 in **3i**, indicated the presence of halogens.

In other compounds, molecular ion peaks M^+ corresponded to the calculated molecular mass of the compounds. The results of the elemental analyses were found to be satisfactory within the permissible limits of errors (Table 1).

Antimicrobial activity : All the synthesized compounds (**3a-l**) were screened for relative antibacterial activity against the Gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* and the Gram-negative bacteria, *Enterobacter cloacae* and

Pseudomonas aeruginosa by taking reference drug as Vancomycin, Cefoperazone/Sulbactam, Meropenem, respectively and antifungal activity against the fungus, *Candida albicans* with Fluconazole as reference drug, at the concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{disc}$. The Paper Disc Method²⁷ was used. The results of antimicrobial activity are indicated in the form of activity index (Table 3).

$$\text{Activity index} = \frac{\text{Zone of inhibition exhibited by test compound}}{\text{Zone of inhibition exhibited by the reference compound}}$$

Most of the compounds were found to show moderate relative activity with respect to the reference compound in 36 h incubation period, against the Gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus*. The compound 10-chloro-6a,7-dihydro-6-(4-methoxyphenyl)-7-(3-nitrophenyl)-6H-[1]benzopyrano[3,4-c][1,5]benzothiazepine, **3b**, showed one and half times higher activity (activity index = 1.54). Against Gram-negative bacteria, *Enterobacter cloacae* out of the twelve new compounds, **3a-l**, the compound **3a** was found to exhibit activity equal to that of the reference (activity index = 1) compound. Most of the compounds were found to show equal or higher antifungal activity (activity index ≥ 1) than that of the reference compound. Greater relative activity against *Candida albicans* was exhibited by **3e**, **3h**, **3j** and **3l**.

Table 3. Antimicrobial activity of **3a-l**
(Zone of inhibition in mm)

Compd.	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Enterobacter cloacae</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	<i>Candida albicans</i>
3a	11 (1.00)	18 (1.00)	14 (1.00)	8 (0.66)
3b	17 (1.54)	12 (0.66)	-	11 (0.91)
3c	15 (1.36)	13 (0.72)	12 (0.85)	12 (1.00)
3d	10 (0.90)	-	9 (0.64)	11 (0.91)
3e	13 (1.18)	17 (0.94)	10 (0.71)	15 (1.25)
3f	14 (1.27)	-	11 (0.78)	12 (1.00)
3g	8 (0.72)	-	7 (0.50)	12 (1.00)
3h	11 (1.00)	16 (0.88)	13 (0.92)	15 (1.25)
3i	15 (1.36)	-	11 (0.78)	-
3j	14 (1.27)	12 (0.66)	12 (0.85)	13 (1.08)
3k	10 (0.90)	12 (0.66)	11 (0.78)	-
3l	-	14 (0.77)	9 (0.64)	15 (1.25)

Values in parentheses represent activity index.

Zone of inhibition of Vancomycin for *Staphylococcus aureus* is 11 mm.

Zone of inhibition of Cefoperazone/Sulbactam for *Enterobacter cloacae* is 18 mm.

Zone of inhibition of Meropenem for *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* is 14 mm.

Zone of inhibition of Fluconazole for *Candida albicans* is 12 mm.

Experimental

Melting points of all the reported compounds are uncorrected. Homogeneity of the compounds was checked by TLC on silica gel 'G' coated glass plates, using benzene : ethanol : aq. ammonia (50%) in the ratio 7 : 2 : 1 as solvent system. The IR spectra were taken in KBr pellets on a Perkin-Elmer RXI FTIR spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker DRX-300 (300 MHz FT NMR with low and high temperature facility) instrument. TMS was used as internal standard and CDCl₃ as the solvent.

The FAB mass spectra were recorded on JEOL-SX-102 (FAB)/Da-600 mass spectrometer/Data system using Argon/Xenon (6 kv, 10 mA) as the FAB gas. The accelerating voltage was 10 kV and spectra were recorded at room temperature. *m*-Nitrobenzyl alcohol (NBA) was used as the matrix. Microestimations for carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen and sulfur were carried out in elemental analyzer, Carlo Erba 1108. The spectral and elemental analyses were carried out at the Sophisticated Analytical Instrumentation Facility, Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow.

Six 5-substituted-2-aminobenzenethiols²⁸ (**1a-f**) and 3-(3-nitrobenzylidene)flavanone²⁹ (**2b**) were prepared by literature reported methods.

3-(3-Nitrobenzylidene)-4'-methoxyflavanone (2a) : Equimolar quantities of 4'-methoxyflavanone (0.01 mol, 2.54 g) and 3-nitrobenzaldehyde (0.01 mol, 1.51 g) were dissolved in ice-cold ethanol saturated with dry HCl separately, then mixed together with stirring. Dry hydrogen chloride was passed in the reaction mixture with stirring till its color changed from light yellow to red and then kept it in refrigerator for 48 h. The crude thus obtained was crystallized from dry methanol to afford shiny yellow needle shaped crystals of 3-(3-nitrobenzylidene)-4'-methoxyflavanone [**2a**, m.p. 85 °C, *R*_f 0.65, yield, 2.82 g (73%); IR (KBr) : 3010 (Ar C-H), 2920 (Aliphatic C-H), 1675 (C=O), 1612 (C=C), 1500, 1469, 1360, 1300 (Ar skeletal); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 3.87 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.46 (s, C₂-H), 7.91 (s, =C-H), 7.93 (s, C₅-H), 6.91-7.88 (m, aromatic 11H) (Found : C, 71.29; H, 4.46; N, 3.58. Calcd. for C₂₃H₁₇NO₅ (387) : C, 71.31; H, 4.42; N, 3.62%).

6a,7-Dihydro-6-(4-methoxyphenyl)-10-methyl-7-(3-nitrophenyl)-6H[1]benzopyrano[3,4-c][1,5]benzothiazepine (3d) : 2-Amino-5-methylbenzenethiol (**1d**, 0.139 g, 0.001 mol) and 3-(3-nitrobenzylidene)-4'-methoxyflavanone (**2a**, 0.001 mol, 0.387 g) were dissolved in dry ethanol (15 mL) containing catalytic amount of TFA and mixed gradually with continuous stirring. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 7 h, till its color changed from brown to blackish brown. It was concentrated and cooled to obtain the crude solid, which was washed with petroleum ether, dried and crystallized from dry ethanol to give *6a,7-dihydro-6-(4-methoxyphenyl)-10-methyl-7-(3-*

nitrophenyl)-6*H*[1]benzopyrano[3,4-*c*][1,5]benzothiazepine; **3d**, m.p. 126–27 °C; $R_f = 0.82$, yield, 0.309 g (60.82%); IR (KBr) : 1311 cm^{-1} (C–O–C), 1604 cm^{-1} (C=N); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) : δ 3.85 (3H, s), 3.37 (dd, $\text{C}_{6a}\text{-H}$, J_1 12.2, J_2 1.2), 4.91 (d, $\text{C}_7\text{-H}$, J 12.2), 5.05 (d, $\text{C}_7\text{-H}$, J 1.2), 2.40 (3H, s, $\text{C}_{10}\text{-XH}$), 6.88–7.97 (m, aromatic 15H) (Found : C, 75.60; H, 6.41. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{S}$ (508) : C, 70.85; H, 4.76%).

Compounds **3a-c**, **3e-l** were prepared following the similar procedure.

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References

- R. N. Brogdon, R. C. Heel, T. M. Speight and G. S. Avery, *Drugs*, 1980, **20**, 161.
- J. D. Wildin, B. J. Pleuvry, G. E. Mawer, T. Onon and L. Millingtonin, *Br. J. Clin. Pharmacol.*, 1990, **29**, 169.
- R. D. Heilman, F. W. Bauer and J. P. Dawanzo, *Curr. Ther. Res. Clin. Exp.*, 1974, **16**, 1022.
- K. Rickels, *Acta Psychiatrica Scandinavica*, 1986, **332**, 132.
- K. T. Oikkola and J. Ahonen, *Handb. Exp. Pharmacol.*, 2008, **182**, 335.
- A. M. Weisman, M. E. Berman and S. P. Taylor, *Int. Clin. Psychopharmacol.*, 1998, **13**, 183.
- G. D. Burrows, P. Dumovic, J. A. Smith, T. Norman and K. Maguire, *Med. J. Aust.*, 1977, **2**, 525.
- D. L. Seger, *J. Toxicol. Clin. Toxicol.*, 2004, **42**, 209.
- W. Werner, K. Wholrace, W. Gutchi, W. Jungstand and W. Roemer, *Folia Haematol.*, 1981, **108**, 637 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1982, **96**, 135313g).
- F. Clemence, D. Frachet, H. Hamon and S. Jouquey, *Eur. Pat. Appl. EP.*, 1990, **394**, 101 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1991, **114**, 164292v).
- A. Ooishi, M. Takeda, H. Nakajima and H. Nagao, *Jpn. Kukai Tokkyo Koho JP*, 61262, 1986, 520 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1987, **106**, 1494478b).
- I. Kataue, N. Furukawa, H. Lizuba, T. Nishina and I. Shirakawa, *Jpn. Kokai Tokkyo Koho JP*, 60, 139, 1985, 6682 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1986, **104**, 68893q).
- S. Diocot, S. Richard, M. Baldy Mouliniar, J. Nargeot and J. Valmier, *Pfluegers Arch.*, 1995, 431, 10 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1994, **124**(17), 219945z).
- S. M. Panesar, M. J. Hagerty, K. A. Kane and R. M. Wadsworth, *J. Auton. Pharmacol.*, 1995, **15**, 107.
- M. J. Hagerty, S. M. Panesar, R. M. Wadsworth and K. A. Kane, *Gen. Pharmac.*, 1995, **26**, 1349.
- U. C. Pant, A. Bhatia, M. Sati, H. Chandra, A. Dandia and S. Pant, *Indian J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 2000, **9**, 233.
- U. C. Pant, H. Chandra, S. Goyal, P. Sharma and S. Pant, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2006, **45**, 752.
- U. C. Pant, H. Chandra, S. Goyal and S. Pant, *Phosphorus, Sulfur and Silicon*, 2005, **180**, 559.
- B. S. Sharma, A. Bhatia and U. C. Pant, *Indian J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1998, **8**, 157.
- M. Upreli, S. Pant, A. Dandia and U. C. Pant, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1997, **36**, 1181.
- S. Pant, H. Chandra, P. Sharma and U. C. Pant, *Indian J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 2006, **15**, 289.
- S. Pant, P. Sharma, B. S. Sharma and U. C. Pant, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2007, **46**, 1537.
- L. Wang, S. Chen, Z. Xu, L. Yu, Q. Wang, Y. Xie, Y. Chen, W. Wang and H. Zhang, *Zhongguo Bingli Shengli Zazhi*, 2002, **18**, 1081 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 2003, **139**, 301641s).
- W. Kostowski, W. Dyr and O. Pucilowski, *Pol. J. Pharmacol. Pharm.*, 1990, **42**, 121 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1991, **114**, 35832x).
- C. L. Cramer, M. L. Stagnitto, M. A. Knowles and G. C. Palmer, *Life Sci.*, 1994, **54**, PL271 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1994, **120**, 261195x).
- S. J. Czuezwara, A. Ckodkańska, Z. Kleinrok, U. Maliek and E. J. Wojtowicz, *Eur. J. Pharmacol.*, 1990, **176**, 75 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1990, **112**, 132271n).
- R. J. Hay, *J. Antimicro. Chemotherap.*, 1991, **28**, 35.
- S. Pant, P. Sharma, B. Singhal and D. Saxena, *Indian J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 2009, **19**, 5.
- D. Dattarya, Dhavale, P. Joshi and K. G. Marathe, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1987, 449.